

NUMERICAL EVALUATION OF THE THERMAL FIELD IN SOLIDIFICATION OF COMPOSITES MATERIALS

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SUMMARY: An evaluation of the thermal field in metallic matrix composites reinforced with ceramic particles is given. In the same context, using the energy band theory it is evaluated the force due the solidification front, on the ceramic particles.

KEYWORDS: thermal field, aluminium metal matrix, incorporation-expulsion phenomena, Seebeck effect

1. INTRODUCTION

In the present work it is showed that the analysis of the thermal field, can give information's about the shape of the solidification front. The numerical method used is triangle schema, a finite differences method. Using the energy-band theory it can be studding the incorporation-expulsion phenomena [1,2,3,4] at the metal matrix-non-metal component interface. Through Seebeck effect it can be associated a difference of potential to the thermal gradient, present in solidification process. It can be done a force evaluation at the interface, outcome being in a good agreement with experimental observation.

2. THERMAL FIELD ANALYSIS

The equations describing the thermal field inside a solidifying material [5], developed from the Fourier's law (neglecting the convective transport) and the equation of thermal flow balance, have the form:

$$\frac{\partial T_{l,s}}{\partial t} = \frac{k_{l,s}}{\rho_{l,s} \cdot c_{l,s}} \cdot \Delta T_{l,s} \quad (1)$$

where T is the temperature, t is the time, $K_{l,s}$ is the thermal conductivity coefficient for the liquid and solid phase respectively, $\rho_{l,s}$ is the density of the two phases, $c_{l,s}$ is the specific heat for the two phases respectively, and Δ stands for the Laplacean. The difficulty in analytical solving these equation comes from the thermal source representing by the solidifying front, the balance equation at the separation of two phases being, in one dimensional case:

$$k_l \frac{\partial T_l(X, t)}{\partial x} = k_s \frac{\partial T_s(X, t)}{\partial x} + \lambda \cdot \rho_l \cdot \frac{\partial X}{\partial t} \quad (2)$$

where $X=X(t)$ is the coordinate of the solidification front, λ the solidification heat and $\partial X / \partial t$ the advance speed of the solidifying front.

Solution of these equation have only been obtained for certain types of boundary conditions, the mostly known [5] indicating a dependence of the form:

$$X(t) = K\sqrt{t} \quad (3)$$

where K is a constant depending on the proprieties of the studied material.

In a first stage, the numerical integration of the equations (1) with boundary condition (2) is proposed. The boundary conditions are determinate by the initial temperature (for example 800°C for aluminium) and the equation of the thermal balance at the melting/moulding box interface respectively. In these equations appear constants such as: initial temperature, thermal proprieties and size of moulding box, the coefficient of surroundings thermal transfer [5] ($t_f = 20^{\circ}\text{C}$, $k_f = 397\text{ W/Km}$, $d=0,01\text{m}$, $\alpha=6 \cdot 10^4\text{W/m}^2/\text{K}$). At the same time, the constants characterising the solidifying metal (aluminium) are also considered as known variables ($t_{\text{solidif. Al}} = 660^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\rho_s=2700\text{ kg/m}^3$, $\rho_L=2385\text{ kg/m}^3$, $k_L=94\text{W/m/K}$, $k_S=238\text{ W/m/K}$, $c_L=1080\text{ J/kg/k}$, $c_S=1080\text{ J/kg/k}$, $\lambda=387,8\text{ kJ/kg}$) [6].

If one performs the integration in one dimensional case, when the size of moulding box is considered much larger than other two, we shall get an additional symmetry - connected condition: the thermal gradient in the symmetry plan is zero.

The utilised scheme is with finite differences, known as triangle explicit scheme, or Schmidt formula [7]:

$$T_j^{n+1} = \beta T_{j-1}^n + (1 - 2\beta)T_j^n + \beta T_{j+1}^n \quad (4)$$

where:

$$\beta = \frac{\alpha_{l,s} \Delta t}{\Delta x^2} \quad (5)$$

In the preview relation $\alpha_{l,s}$ denotes the fraction in front of the Laplacean (1), and Δx and ΔT are the intervals of space and time division.

The resulting space-time configuration of the thermal field is presented in figure 1a) and the spatial distribution of temperature for a given moment of time in figure 1b).

Fig. 1: a) Space-time distribution of thermal field; b) Temperature distribution for a given time moment

This representation confirm the existence of a maximum value of temperature in the very place where the solid-liquid interface is located at a given moment, obviously determined by the latent heat elimination. In the vicinity of the solidification front, the thermal gradient is maximum. At the same time, the temporal dependence of the solidifying front coordinates agrees with the equation (3).

3. THE ELECTRICAL FORCE ACTING ON THE PARTICLE.

When two different phases are in contact they are generally separated by a very thin layer whose properties differ from the properties of the two basic phases. The energy of the interface layer is higher than the inner energy, the energy excess, usually known as the interface energy, represents the energy of the unit surface.

An essential parameter in the study of the contact phenomena [8] is the extraction work ϕ_F [9], specific to each type of material and representing the energy necessary to extract in vacuum an electron with the energy equal to the maximum energy at O.K. (Fermi energy). In the case of the contact between two solids, due to different extraction works, a carriers transfer occurs, resulting in the appearance of a double layer of spatial electric charge. In the case of the metal-ceramics contact, this layer extend less in the metal due to a higher electron concentration.

At the equilibrium a interval electric field results with its maximum potential, called barrier potential V_b :

$$V_b = \frac{|\Phi_{\text{non-metal}} - \Phi_{\text{metal}}|}{e} \quad (6)$$

where e is the elementary electric charge.

We shall calculate the superficial charge density for a metal-ceramics system. In order to deduce the expressions of the electronic potential, $V(x)$, the charge density, $\rho(x)$, and space charge layer thickness in the semiconductor, d ; we shall use the Poisson's equation [8] with the Ox axis perpendicular to the contact plane.

$$d^2V/dx^2 = -\rho(x)/\epsilon \quad (7)$$

where ϵ is the dielectric permittivity of the medium, and

$$\rho(x) = e \cdot n \cdot \exp\left(\frac{eV}{KT}\right) \quad (8)$$

where n is the intrinsic charge carrier concentration in the non - metal at the temperature T , and K is the Boltzman's constant.

Solving the Eq. (7) with the boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} x = 0, V(0) &= V_b \\ x = d, V(d) &= 0, \left. \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} \right|_{x=d} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

one obtains

$$V(x) = -\frac{KT}{e} \ln \left[A \left(\frac{x^2}{2} - dx + \frac{\exp\left(\frac{eV_b}{KT}\right)}{A} \right) \right] \quad (10)$$

where

$$A = \left(\frac{e}{KT}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{en}{\epsilon}\right), \text{ and } d = \sqrt{\frac{2}{A} [\exp\left(\frac{eV_b}{KT}\right) - 1]} \quad (11)$$

The superficial charge density in metal, in the interface immediate vicinity, has the expression

$$\sigma_M = \int_0^d \rho(x)V(x)dx = C \cdot |V_b|^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

where C is a constant which depends on the materials type.

The presence of a thermal gradient in solidifying metals determine a potential gradient [9] (Seebeck effect):

$$\text{grad}(V) = \alpha \cdot \text{grad}(T) \quad (13)$$

where α is the Seebeck coefficient. Thus, assimilating the particles as punctual charges, the force acting on them is given by the relation

$$F = \sigma_M \cdot \frac{\pi d_0^2}{4} \cdot \text{grad}(V) = \sigma_M \frac{\pi d_0^2}{4} \cdot \alpha \cdot \text{grad}(T) \quad (14)$$

where d_0 is the particle diameter. Considering $Q_M \sim 10^{-12}$ C, $d_0 \sim 10^{-7}$ m, $\alpha \sim 10^{-5}$ V/m, $\text{grad}(T) = 10^4$ °C/m [10], this force have the dimension 10^{-11} N, the same with the force considered in SDKM [4] and SRP [3] models.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The main results of the present work are as follows:

- i) the thermal gradient in solidifying metals has the maximum value in the vicinity of the solidification front and value increase towards the centre of the sample;
- ii) the force which is acting on the particle depends essential on the particles dimensions, on the type of the materials in contact, and on the thermal gradient;
- iii) under these circumstances, the small particles are incorporated easiest, the best incorporation being in the proximity of the sample margins.

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